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<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejlhss.v1i7.760>**THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON
THE QUALITY OF INTERPERSONAL
COMMUNICATION IN DAILY LIFE****Tazkia Aulia Kamila**

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Abstract: The development of technology today is very directly proportional to the survival of human beings in their level of needs and development. In recent decades, one of the technologies that has experienced significant advancements is Communication Technology. Communication is an integral part of human behavior, and almost all aspects of human life involve communication in various forms. Communication technology is changing the way people interact and has a number of significant impacts on the quality of communication. This journal examines how communication technology has an impact on the quality of interpersonal and professional communication and its implications for society.

Keywords: Impact, Technology, Communication and Information, Interpersonal, Individual

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license**Intoduction**

In connection with the development of communication technology, there are also more and more new innovations such as the increasing variety of communication technologies that can help facilitate communication patterns in our lives, even in this era many humans use this communication technology as the main communication medium used daily. Gradually, telegrams, letters, and landline phones began to change to more sophisticated technology such as mobile phones or mobile phones that can be used regardless of distance and time.

In the midst of the development of this communication technology, there is technology that can help provide various information needed by the community, namely internet technology. The existence of internet technology and phenomenal communication developments have certainly opened a new chapter in the increasingly modern life of people to obtain information independently. The presence of Internet Technology itself has even entered remote areas and formed its own communication activities (Nurudin, 2012).

Apart from these developments, of course, we are also faced with a consequence. Almost most of the people in this world cannot be separated from the dependence on internet technology, the community also becomes critical and does not want to know about the situation and other positive things that are currently developing.

This communication and information technology has even entered various aspects of people's lives. For example, in today's era, the relationships built between individuals are not solely through physical but have reached the 'interface' stage. Interface itself is a program that allows users to interact with their devices directly or through networks connected by technological devices. According to Ellis (Littlejohn & Foss, 2009), media will shape behavior and thinking for anyone who is contaminated with the existence of technology in its time. This technological advancement is really felt and recognized as being able to provide benefits and convenience for humans (Nasrullah, 2012).

Interpersonal communication or interpersonal communication is the process of exchanging information, ideas, and feelings between two or more people. In the context of modern technology, communication technology has had some major impact on interpersonal communication. Including:

1. Communication technologies such as telephone, text messaging, email, and social media allow individuals to communicate easily without being restricted by geographical distance. People can talk and exchange messages with anyone around the world quickly and efficiently.
2. The variety of communication platforms available (WhatsApp, Telegram, Instagram, etc.) allows individuals to choose the medium that best suits their communication preferences, including text, audio, and video.
3. Communication technology also expands the possibilities of social interaction. For example, social media allows individuals to interact with friends, family, and even strangers in ways that were previously impossible.
4. Technology is improving connectivity, but there is debate about its impact on personal relationships. There is also an argument that excessive use of technology can degrade the quality of face-to-face interactions.
5. With the development of technology, communication styles have also changed. Text messages, emojis, and other forms have become the everyday language of communication for many people, influencing the way we interact and convey emotions.
6. Communication technology also facilitates collaboration between individuals or groups that are in different locations. This means that individuals can work on projects and develop ideas together without having to meet in person.
7. The use of communication technology also poses challenges related to ethics and data protection. For example, data protection, information security, and the misuse of communication platforms are the main problems in the digital era.

While communication technology brings many benefits, it also brings some important negative impacts that must be considered:

1. While technology allows us to connect with people around the world, overuse can lead to social isolation. Individuals may prefer to communicate through technology rather than interact directly socially.
2. Communication technology also often causes concentration disorders, especially when working or doing activities that require a high level of concentration.
3. Some people are addicted to communication technologies such as social media and messaging apps. Focusing too much on reactions and attention online can lead to mental health problems such as anxiety and depression.
4. Digital communication also often lacks rich nonverbal contexts, such as facial expressions and body language. This can lead to misunderstandings and misinterpretations of the message conveyed.
5. The use of communication technology increases security and privacy risks. In a connected digital environment, personal data can be misused and the risk of information leakage is high.
6. Access to technology is increasing, but the digital divide still exists between those with adequate access and technology skills and those who don't. This can exacerbate economic and social disparities.

In summary, communication technology has changed the landscape of communication between individuals significantly. While there are many benefits, it is important that we still consider the social, psychological and ethical implications and adapt to changes in the way we interact and communicate. In conclusion, communication technology has significantly changed the way we live, work, and interact with each other. Despite the many benefits, it is important to

consider the social, economic, and cultural impacts they entail and efforts to minimize their negative impacts.

The purpose of holding this study is intended to determine the influence of the intensity of the use of communication technology on the intimacy of Interpersonal Communication. It is hoped that this research will help us understand how communication technologies, such as social media, instant messaging apps, and other digital platforms, affect the way people interact with each other. In addition, it is also hoped that the results of this research can provide insight to technology developers about how their products affect users. This can help in designing better technology, which supports healthy and productive communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical review is a theoretical approach that will be used by researchers to explain the problems in this study. In this study, the researcher will use the Theory of Media Ecology as the theoretical review.

Media ecology theory is an approach that studies how media and communication technologies affect society and culture. This theory emphasizes that the media is not only a channel or tool for conveying messages, but also as an environment that shapes the way we interact, think, and understand the world. Marshall McLuhan, a media and communication theorist, is famous for the phrase "Medium Is The Message". This concept is at the heart of his theory which explains how the medium or media itself—not just the content or message conveyed—has a significant impact on society. The symbiotic relationship with media technology refers to the mutually beneficial interaction between humans and technology. In this context, media technology and humans influence and adapt to each other.

Media shapes and regulates culture. This is called the theory of media ecology. The concept of symbiosis between humans and technology put forward by Marshall McLuhan is at the core of the theory of media ecology. Humans create technology, and technology shapes humans.

The Theory of Media Ecology put forward by Marshall McLuhan does focus on the principle that technology and media have a profound and comprehensive influence on society and individuals.

The previous research has been carried out by Novy Purnama (2012) and Syahrudin (2020).

1. Research: The Impact of Communication Technology Development on Socio-Cultural Life by Novy Purnama (2012)

The main theme in this study may be to explore how the development of communication technology affects the social and cultural aspects of society. By looking at the impact of communication technology on social norms, social relationships, and changes in community culture. The development of technology is directly proportional to the development and level of human survival needs. One form of technology that has experienced rapid development over the past decade is information technology. This cannot be separated from the need for humans to communicate, because the essence of human behavior is to communicate.

2. Research: The Influence of Information and Communication Technology on the Effectiveness of Interpersonal Communication of Students by Syahrudin (2020)

The main theme in this study is likely to focus on how information and communication technology affects the way students communicate interpersonally. By assessing how technological tools such as social media, messaging applications, and digital platforms affect the quality and effectiveness of interpersonal communication. The high level of human interaction with screens or screen technology (cellphones, computers) as part of the need for information gives rise to a human behavior that is more concerned with face-to-screen relationships than face-to-face. The research problem is how information and communication technology affects the effectiveness of interpersonal communication among students in Kendari City. The purpose of the research is to find

out the influence of Information and Communication Technology on the effectiveness of interpersonal communication among students in Kendari City and what impact it has caused from the development of information and communication technology. The location of the research is a university located in the Kendari City area. Data collection was carried out using questionnaires (questionnaires), interviews and documentation. The respondents were 75 people, and the research informants were seven people determined purposively. The results showed that variable X (information and communication technology) affected variable Y (effectiveness of interpersonal communication) in students in Kendari City where the variables together had an influence of 0.596, located between values of 0.50-0.69 which showed that the value of the correlation coefficient was in a strong relationship.

Based on the previous research journals that the researcher has described above, the difference between the journals above and the journals What the researcher researches broadly is that in this journal the researcher does not only focus on interpersonal communication and social media, but this journal focuses on the use of social media itself in interpersonal communication, where social media has benefits for building interpersonal communication.

Research can be said to be one way to develop or advance a system. The system in question is an existing order or information. The current research method is a scientific way of obtaining information for certain purposes and uses, Djollong, A.F. (2014). In this study, the researcher uses the type of quantitative research is a research approach that prioritizes the collection and analysis of numerical data to test hypotheses or answer research questions. Djollong, A.F. (2014) said that quantitative research methods are research that is widely found in the field of data collection techniques in the field.

The time span of this research was carried out in 3 months, namely from May 2024 to July 2024 which included data collection, data management and writing of research results. The population in this study itself is the closest relatives of the author with vulnerable ages of 21-29 years from various professions totaling 31 people.

The sampling method that will be used by the author in this study is the non-probability sampling method, with the census method technique or also called saturated samples. According to Sugiyono (2019), census or saturated sampling is a sample selection technique in which all members of the population are used as samples. Since the population of this study does not exceed 100 respondents, the author uses 100% of the existing population or 31 respondents. Therefore, the use of the entire population without the withdrawal of research samples as a unit of observation is called the census method.

Data collection is indeed one of the most important research activities because it is the basis for the analysis and interpretation of research results. Data collection in research must always be considered in such a way as to ensure that the data obtained can be maintained at its level of validity and reliability. Even with valid and reliable research tools, the data collected is useless if you don't pay attention to the research process.

The use of questionnaires is a very common data collection technique in different types of research, especially in quantitative research. A questionnaire is a tool or instrument used to collect data from respondents through a series of questions that have been prepared pre-prepared. Questionnaires are often used in research to obtain information about an individual's opinions, attitudes, knowledge, or characteristics. Designing questionnaire questions based on variable indicators and providing appropriate alternative answers is key to obtaining accurate and relevant data. This questionnaire was developed with a Likert scoring scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Result and Discussion

In quantitative research, the data is often in the form of numbers collected through questionnaires or other instruments. Once the data is collected, statistical software such as SPSS

(Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) is used to analyze the data. This study also has the purpose of determining the influence of the intensity of the use of communication technology on the intimacy of Interpersonal Communication. With the purpose based, data was collected using the Questionnaire method as many as 31 respondents who are daily dealing with Communication Technology such as gadgets. The distribution of this questionnaire was carried out behind closed doors using Pie Chart. This study uses an independent variable, namely the Impact of Communication Technology and also a dependent variable, namely the Quality of Interpersonal Communication.

A. Characteristics Responden

In research, understanding the characteristics of respondents is an important step in gaining deeper insights into their backgrounds. By knowing these characteristics, researchers can better analyze the data and provide relevant context to the research findings. Here are some common ways to collect and analyze respondent characteristics based on gender, age, and occupation:

1. Gender Characteristics

Table 4.1

Gender Characteristic Testing

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	19	61.3%
Woman	12	38.7%
Total	31	100%

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Based on Table 4.1 above, this study used 31 samples. So in terms of gender, the total gender integrity is 61.3% male and 38.7% female.

2. Characteristic Profesi

Table 4.2

Profession Characteristics Testing

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Student	1	3.2%
Student	10	32.3%
Official	20	64.5%
Total	31	100%

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Based on Table 4.2 above, as many as 31 respondents had different professions. 3.2% as a student, 32.3% as a student, and 64.5% as an employee.

3. Age Characteristics

Table 4.3

Profession Characteristics Testing

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
< 19 yrs	2	6.4%
20 yrs	2	6.4%

21 yrs	8	25.8%
22 yrs	11	35.5%
>22 yrs	8	25.8%
Total	31	100%

Source : Processed Data, 2024

The results of the analysis of Table 4.3 provide an overview that from the sample taken as many as 31 respondents among students, students, and employees, it turns out that in terms of age there are 5 groupings and the most taken at the age of 22 years old is 35.5%, then those who are 21 years old and over 22 years old as much as 25.8% and the last one is 20 years old and less than 19 years old as much as 6.4%.

B. Jawban Respondent Narrative

Table 4.4

Results of Explanation of Respondents' Answers

Variable	Average
The Impact of Communication Technology	
There is a difference in the quality of communication between the generation that grew up with digital technology and the generation that did not	3,76
Communication technology affects the effectiveness of communication in professional and business contexts	3,83
Communication technology supports team collaboration and cooperation within the organization	3,93
Communication technology hinders team collaboration and cooperation within organizations	3,17
Communication technology leads to an increase in misinterpretation and miscommunication	3,37
Communication Technology is very helpful in maintaining long-distance relationship communication	4
You interact more often through Gadgets than face-to-face	3,63
Your communication is smoother when you do it through a gadget than face-to-face	3,57
Chat sharpens interpersonal communication skills	3,77

Quality of Interpersonal Communication	
Digital communication technologies (such as social media, instant messaging and email) greatly affect the quality of interpersonal communication	3,8
The use of Communication Technology reduces the ability to listen and understand deeply in face-to-face conversations	3,63
Communication technologies affect interpersonal relationships and empathy between individuals	3,7

Source : Processed Data, 2024

From the questionnaire data taken with the percentage 1 = strongly disagree 2 = disagree 3 = neutral 4 = agree 5 = strongly agree, then based on Table 4.4 it can be seen that there are 2 variables studied, namely the Impact of Communication Technology and the Quality of Inter-individual Communication. By looking at the respondents' answers evenly on the Communication

Technology Impact variable with an average value of 3.67, it means that the tendency to agree. This means that there is a difference in the quality of communication between the generation that grew up with digital technology and the generation that does not have communication technology affecting the effectiveness of communication in professional and business contexts, communication technology supports team collaboration and cooperation in organizations, communication technology inhibits team collaboration and cooperation in organizations, communication technology causes an increase in misinterpretation and miscommunication, communication technology is very Helping in maintaining long-distance communication, you interact more often through Gadgets than face-to-face, your communication is smoother if you do it through Gadgets rather than face-to-face, and chatting hones interpersonal communication skills is justified by Respondents, which means that they agree that in this day and age, they communicate more through mobile phones than face-to-face. Even in the last point, the point "Chatting hones interpersonal communication skills" has an average of 3.77 which is very close to the approval score. That means that behind the negative impact, this technology still has a positive impact because some people think that with more Chats on Social Media, it really hones their skills when communicating face-to-face.

Meanwhile, in the perception of Interpersonal Communication Quality, Reponden also tends to agree with the statement that digital communication technology (such as social media, instant messaging and email) greatly affects the quality of interpersonal communication, the use of Communication Technology reduces the ability to listen and understand deeply in face-to-face conversations, communication technology affects interpersonal relationships and empathy between individuals. This states that in addition to Chatting can hone individual skills, it turns out that communicating too often through Communication Technology also greatly affects our lack of ability to listen and understand face-to-face conversations in depth. Therefore, it is good if we start balancing ourselves in using communication technology and in interpersonal communication.

Table 4.5
Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	R Calculate	R Table	Information
The Impact of Communication Technology	DTK1	0,639	0,195	Valid
	DTK2	0,713	0,195	Valid
	DTK3	0,713	0,195	Valid
	DTK4	0,672	0,195	Valid
	DTK5	0,646	0,195	Valid
	DTK6	0,747	0,195	Valid
	DTK7	0,723	0,195	Valid
	DTK8	0,642	0,195	Valid
	DTK9	0,657	0,195	Valid
Quality of Interpersonal Communication	KKA1	0,610	0,195	Valid
	KKA2	0,633	0,195	Valid
	KKA3	0,722	0,195	Valid

Table 4.5 above shows that there are two variables that represent the research material. The two variables studied have nine and three question items for both independent and dependent variables, respectively. It can be seen that the value of r calculation is greater than that of r table. This allows you to declare that the data taken in the field is valid.

Table 4.6
Reliability Test Results

Variable	<i>Cronbah's Alpha</i>	<i>Role of Thumb</i>	Information
The Impact of Communication Technology	0,625	0,6	Reliebel
Quality of Communication Interpersonal	0,653	0,6	Reliebel

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Table 4.6 shows that in this test it is carried out variable, not in terms of question items on each variable that can be seen, the result is that the value of the cronbah's alpha is greater than 0.6, then it can be said to be reliable.

Table 4.7
Multiple Regression Analysis Test Results

Variable	Coefficient β	Santadar Error
Constant	2,416	2003
The Impact of Technology Communication	0,269	0,118
Quality of Communication Interpersonal	0,214	0,0093

Source : Processed Data, 2024

Based on table 4.7, the data is produced that the β coefficient is a form of a regression equation that can be produced as follows:

$$Y = 2.416 + 0.269 X_1 + 0.214 X_2 + e$$

Table 4.8
Reliability Test Results

Variable	T count	<i>Sig</i>	Information
The Impact of Communication Technology	2,276	0,025	Signifikan
Quality of Communication Interpersonal	2,300	0,024	Signifikan
F Calculate	16,871	R	0,588
F Sig	0,000	<i>R Square</i>	0,345

Source : Processed Data, 2024

a. Model Accuracy Testing (Test F)

This test was carried out with the aim of finding out how far the free variable is used to be able to explain the bound variable. In this study, the Impact of Communication Technology (X1),

and the Quality of Interpersonal Communication (X2) are stimulantly related to the bound variable, namely in Daily Life (Y), and determine whether the model is appropriate or not. In this study, the author obtained the result: Based on table 4.8 the F value is 16.871 with F sig. 0.000 where F sig. 0.000 is less than 0.05 that means Ho is rejected. It can also be interpreted if simultaneously the Impact of Communication Technology (X1) and the Quality of Communication Between Individuals (X2) have a significant impact on daily life (Y).

b. Significant Testing (t-Test)

Significance testing, or significance testing, is a statistical method used to determine whether the results of a study or experiment are strong enough to show any real effects or relationships in a broader population, or whether those results may have occurred by chance. To provide 54 interpretations of the t-test can be explained in Table 4.8 is: The calculated t-value generated on the Communication Technology Impact variable is 2.276 with a sig of 0.025. The results of the analysis. 0.025 is less than 0.05, meaning that individually the variables of the impact of communication technology have an important influence on the quality of communication.

c. Determinant Coefficient (R²)

The determination coefficient, often abbreviated as R² is a statistical measure used to assess how well a regression model explains variability in data. This is an important indicator in regression analysis that shows the proportion of variation in dependent variables that can be explained by independent variables. A small R² value means that the ability of the independent variable to explain the variation of the dependent variable is very limited. The R square value of 0.345 (34.5%) can be interpreted that the ability of the Impact of Communication Technology (X1) explains the variation of the Interpersonal Communication Quality variable (X2) by 34.5% and the rest is influenced by other independent variables by 65.5%.

Conclusion

The intensity of the use of communication technology refers to the frequency with which a person communicates with others through technological media. Frequent use of technology can increase openness between individuals, which in turn can strengthen relationships and result in deeper intimacy. Communication technology has a varied impact on the intimacy of interpersonal communication. On the one hand, technology facilitates relationships by providing ease of access, flexibility, and richer ways of self-expression. On the other hand, excessive or unwise use of technology can reduce the depth of interaction, leading to dependability, disruption, and privacy issues.

With this study, it can be concluded that communication technology has a very significant influence in daily life. Frequent communication through technology can reduce face-to-face communication skills, but on the other hand it also hones communication skills in a digital context. Technology allows long-distance communication to continue despite being hindered by distance, and also provides great advantages for many companies in running their businesses. To maximize the benefits of technology in interpersonal communication, it is important to strike a balance between the use of technology and face-to-face interactions, as well as focus on the quality of communication, not just the quantity. The results of the analysis in this study itself show that Communication Technology has a great influence on our daily lives. But apparently, in this study, we can find out that the use of technology also indirectly hones our ability to communicate. In addition, this technology is also able to connect long-distance communication so that interpersonal communication still occurs even though it is blocked by distance. Communication Technology also turns out to help many companies in running their businesses

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